

The Kiselev isotherm for adsorption at the liquid-solid interface: Solving the mystery of negative equilibrium constants

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Abstract

Equilibrium data for aqueous adsorption systems are often correlated using isotherm models originally developed for adsorption at the gas-solid interface. A prominent example is the Langmuir isotherm, which has been used in thousands of investigations to describe the adsorption of dissolved substances at the liquid-solid interface. Another example is the Kiselev isotherm, which was proposed to account for adsorption at the gas-solid interface when adsorbate-adsorbate interactions are significant. Researchers who have applied the Kiselev isotherm to adsorption data for liquid-solid systems were puzzled by the fact that data fittings in most cases returned negative values for the adsorbate-adsorbate association equilibrium constant. It is shown in the present study that the data fitting problem is a direct consequence of misusing the Kiselev isotherm. In all previous studies, the Kiselev isotherm was used to fit type I isotherm data. Because the concept of adsorbate-adsorbate interactions is incompatible with a type I isotherm, fitting the Kiselev isotherm to such data can lead to nonsensical parameter estimates. The Kiselev isotherm was devised to account for type V isotherms exhibiting a sigmoid or S-shaped data trend. Physically meaningful parameter estimates can be obtained if the Kiselev isotherm is applied to type V isotherm data.

1. Introduction

Many isotherm models originally developed for gas-solid adsorption have been used to describe adsorption at the interface of liquid-solid. A classic example is the Langmuir isotherm [1] which provides a practical equation by which aqueous adsorption data can be successfully correlated. Likewise, the Kiselev isotherm—originally proposed for describing adsorption of gases on solid surfaces [2,3]—has been used to describe aqueous adsorption systems in an increasing number of articles. Frequently, the Kiselev isotherm for liquid-phase adsorption is written as Eq. (1), where c is the liquid-phase concentration, θ is the surface coverage, K_1 is the equilibrium constant of adsorption (adsorbate-adsorbent), and K_n is the equilibrium constant of association (adsorbate-adsorbate).

$$K_1 c = \frac{\theta}{(1-\theta)(1+K_n\theta)} \quad (1)$$

To facilitate parameter estimation by linear regression, Eq. (1) is rearranged to the linear form given by Eq. (2). If Eq. (2) is obeyed, a plot of its left-side member against $1/\theta$ should yield a straight line.

$$\frac{1}{(1-\theta)c} = K_1 K_n + K_1 \frac{1}{\theta} \quad (2)$$

To use Eq. (2) for data fitting, one must know the value of θ , which is defined by the ratio q/q_m , where q is the amount adsorbed and q_m is the specific saturation capacity of the adsorbent. Various methods have been used to estimate q_m . For example, the q_m term that appears in simple isotherms such as the Langmuir equation is often used as a surrogate for the q_m parameter in the Kiselev isotherm [4,5]. In this way, the Kiselev isotherm is treated as a two-parameter expression which permits the use of linear regression to estimate the two unknown equilibrium constants K_1 and K_n from experimental data. However, several studies using this parameter estimation approach have obtained some puzzling results. As can be seen

in Table 1, these studies have reported negative equilibrium constants, which have no physical meaning.

So far as the author knows, the problem of obtaining negative equilibrium constants from data fitting has not yet been resolved. Some of the investigators listed in Table 1 were aware that the equilibrium constants should be nonnegative but were unable to clarify the issue [5,12,13]. The intent of this article is to solve this mystery by re-evaluating selected literature isotherm data using a different parameter estimation approach. In this work, the Kiselev isotherm is treated as a three-parameter equation to which a nonlinear regression procedure is applied to extract q_m , K_1 , and K_n from experimental data. Reasons for obtaining a negative estimate for the association equilibrium constant K_n from data fitting are considered. Conditions under which the Kiselev isotherm will yield a positive estimate for K_n are examined.

Table 1. Examples of studies reporting negative equilibrium constants for the Kiselev isotherm.

Reference	Year of publication	K_1	K_n
Ferrandon et al. [4]	1995	Positive	Negative
Hamdaoui and Naffrechoux [5]	2007	Positive/negative	Negative
Bekkouche et al. [6]	2012	Positive	Positive/negative
Yousef et al. [7]	2016	Negative	Negative
Shao and Hall [8]	2016	Positive	Negative
Li et al. [9]	2018	Negative	Negative
Rangabhashiyam and Balasubramanian [10]	2018	Negative	Negative
Rangabhashiyam and Balasubramanian [11]	2018	Positive	Negative
Mokkapati et al. [12]	2018	Negative	Negative
Nayak and Pal [13]	2020	Negative	Positive
Jeyavishnu and Alagesan [14]	2020	Negative	Negative
Mathangi et al. [15]	2021	Positive	Negative

2. Parameter estimation

The unknown parameters of the Kiselev isotherm were estimated using a nonlinear least-squares fitting procedure. The Kiselev isotherm is treated as a nonlinear equation with three adjustable parameters: q_m , K_1 , and K_n . Accordingly, Eq. (1) is rewritten as Eq. (3).

$$K_1 c = \frac{q_m q}{(q_m - q)(q_m + K_n q)} \quad (3)$$

The conventional sum of squared residuals (SSR) for least-squares fitting is defined as the difference between the measured and calculated solid-phase concentrations, given here by Eq. (4), where $q_{exp,i}$ are observed solid-phase concentrations, $q_{cal,i}$ are solid-phase concentrations calculated from the Kiselev isotherm, and m is the number of data points. It is thus necessary to express Eq. (3) in terms of q . Because Eq. (3) is quadratic in q , there are two possible solutions [see Eq. (5)]. Given that q is a nonnegative quantity, Eq. (6) is the appropriate expression to use for parameter estimation. The constraint on the three fitting parameters is the requirement that all values be nonnegative, as a negative uptake capacity or a negative equilibrium constant would have no physical meaning.

$$SSR = \sum_{i=1}^m (q_{exp,i} - q_{cal,i})^2 \quad (4)$$

$$q = \frac{x \pm \sqrt{y}}{z} \quad (5)$$

$$q = \frac{x + \sqrt{y}}{z} \quad (6)$$

where

$$x = K_1 K_n q_m c - K_1 q_m c - q_m$$

$$y = 4K_n (K_1 q_m c)^2 + (q_m + K_1 q_m c - K_1 K_n q_m c)^2$$

$$z = 2K_1 K_n c$$

3. Results

Published isotherm data taken from two reports listed in Table 1 have been used to evaluate the Kiselev isotherm. The isotherm for 4-chlorophenol (4-CP) on an activated carbon adsorbent was obtained from Hamdaoui and Naffrechoux [5]. The isotherm for phenol on an activated carbon adsorbent was taken from Li et al. [9].

3.1. 4-CP isotherm

The batch adsorption of several phenolic compounds by a granular activated carbon adsorbent has been investigated by Hamdaoui and Naffrechoux [5]. The resulting equilibrium data were analyzed using seven isotherm models, the Kiselev isotherm being one of them. Here, the isotherm data set obtained for 4-chlorophenol (4-CP) was re-evaluated. To fit the linearized Kiselev isotherm given by Eq. (2) to the 4-CP data, Hamdaoui and Naffrechoux [5] used three different q_m values to compute θ in Eq. (2). The three q_m values led to different numerical values for K_1 and K_n , but the first constant was positive while the second was negative. An attempt was made here to reproduce a set of their K_1 and K_n values. A theoretical estimation approach used by Hamdaoui and Naffrechoux [5] produced a q_m value of 595.3 mg g⁻¹. Using this q_m value to calculate θ , Eq. (2) was fit to the 4-CP data using the linear regression procedure of Excel. The linear fit with an R^2 value of 0.85 is rather poor, as shown in Fig. 1A. The resulting parameter estimates are $K_1 = 0.26$ L mg⁻¹ and $K_n = -2.07$, which correspond well to the estimates reported by Hamdaoui and Naffrechoux [5] ($K_1 = 0.27$ L mg⁻¹ and $K_n = -2.06$).

Next, the nonlinear version of the Kiselev isotherm with three adjustable parameters [Eq. (6)] was fit to the 4-CP data using a nonlinear least-squares fitting algorithm. The resulting parameter estimates are $q_m = 309$ mg g⁻¹, $K_1 = 0.26$ L mg⁻¹, and $K_n = 7.3E-7$. The q_m value extracted from the experimental data is evidently much smaller than the theoretical q_m value used by Hamdaoui and Naffrechoux [5] in their linear regression analysis. Nevertheless, the K_1 value obtained from the nonlinear fit is similar to their K_1 value. However, the K_n value

obtained from the nonlinear fit is practically zero, indicating that it can be omitted from the parameter estimation process without affecting the quality of fit. As can be seen in Fig. 1B, the nonlinear fit (orange line) is more accurate in tracing the data points than the curve (blue line) computed using the linear regression-generated parameters reported by Hamdaoui and Naffrechoux [5].

Fig. 1. (A) Linear fit of Eq. (2) to observed 4-CP data. (B) The orange line is the nonlinear fit of Eq. (6) to observed 4-CP data and the blue line is the prediction of Eq. (6) calculated using parameter estimates obtained from linear regression. Data of Hamdaoui and Naffrechoux [5].

3.2. Phenol isotherm

A rotating packed bed apparatus has been used by Li et al. [9] to investigate the adsorption of phenol on an activated carbon adsorbent. The resulting data set was fit to six different isotherm models, including the Kiselev isotherm. Using a q_m value of 124.05 mg g^{-1} (estimated from the Freundlich isotherm) to compute θ , the linearized Kiselev isotherm was fit to the phenol data by a linear regression analysis, returning $K_1 = -0.039 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$ and $K_n = -0.491$. To verify their parameter estimates, the linear regression procedure of Excel was used to fit Eq. (2) to the phenol data using their Freundlich q_m value to calculate θ . As Fig. 2A shows, the linear fit with an R^2 score of 0.97 is satisfactory. The resulting estimates for the equilibrium constants are $K_1 = 0.019 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$, and $K_n = -2.047$. Our K_1 estimate is a positive value, which contradicts the negative K_1 value reported by Li et al. [9]. The blue line in Fig. 2B is the prediction of Eq. (6) calculated using our linear regression-generated parameter estimates. It agrees reasonably well with the observed data. However, it was not possible to compute an isotherm curve from Eq. (6) using the Freundlich q_m , negative K_1 , and negative K_n values reported in the work of Li et al. [9]. It appears that their estimates for the two equilibrium constants are suspect.

The nonlinear Kiselev isotherm given by Eq. (6) was fit to the phenol data using a nonlinear least-squares fitting algorithm. The resulting parameter estimates are $q_m = 64 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$, $K_1 = 0.026 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$, and $K_n = 1.6\text{E}-6$. The estimate for q_m is much smaller than the Freundlich q_m value adopted by Li et al. [9]. The K_1 estimate is a positive value, which contradicts the negative K_1 value reported by Li et al. [9]. The K_n value is again effectively zero, indicating that it can be left out in the data fitting process. In Fig. 2B, we compare the nonlinear fit of Eq. (6) and experimental profile for phenol. Good agreement is observed, and the nonlinear fit (orange line) is more accurate than the predicted curve of Eq. (6) (blue line) calculated using our linear regression-generated parameter estimates.

Fig. 2. (A) Linear fit of Eq. (2) to observed phenol data. (B) The orange line is the nonlinear fit of Eq. (6) to observed phenol data and the blue line is the prediction of Eq. (6) calculated using parameter estimates obtained from linear regression. Data of Li et al. [9].

4. Discussion

4.1. 4-CP and phenol isotherms

The isotherm data sets for 4-CP and phenol were subjected to linear regression analyses in the original papers [5,9]. This linear data fitting approach was made possible by using q_m values obtained from other sources as surrogates for the unknown q_m in the Kiselev isotherm. In the present study, q_m values were extracted directly from the 4-CP and phenol data using a nonlinear regression procedure. Our q_m estimates (309 mg g⁻¹ for 4-CP and 64 mg g⁻¹ for

phenol) correspond to the experimental data in the plateau regions of the two isotherms (see Figs. 1B and 2B). The q_m values adopted by the original papers (595.3 mg g⁻¹ for 4-CP and 124.05 mg g⁻¹ for phenol) are about twice the q_m values extracted from the isotherm data. It is operationally incorrect to use inflated q_m values as surrogates for the unknown q_m in the Kiselev isotherm to calculate θ . Therefore, the practice of converting the three-parameter Kiselev isotherm to a two-parameter version to allow data fitting by linear regression is technically unsound. Hereafter, we focus on the nonlinear regression fitting results presented in the previous section.

An important result derived from the nonlinear regression analyses is that the estimate for the association equilibrium constant K_n is practically zero for both data sets. This result implies that the K_n parameter is superfluous when the Kiselev equation is used to fit a type I isotherm, the shape of which is always convex upward, indicating that there are no attractions between molecules of adsorbate and that the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent is finite. In the absence of adsorbate-adsorbate interactions, that is, $K_n = 0$, the Kiselev isotherm reduces to the celebrated Langmuir isotherm [see Eq. (7)]. It can therefore be concluded that one should get the same result when a type I isotherm is fit with the Kiselev or Langmuir equation. To verify this claim, the Langmuir isotherm was fit to the 4-CP and phenol data. In Fig. 3, we compare the Kiselev and Langmuir fits for the two phenolic compounds. For both data sets, Fig. 3 shows that the Langmuir fit displays excellent conformity with the Kiselev fit. It is evident that the Kiselev isotherm with a near zero value for K_n is analogous to the Langmuir isotherm.

$$\theta = \frac{q}{q_m} = \frac{K_1 c}{1 + K_1 c} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3. Comparison of Kiselev and Langmuir fits to observed 4-CP and phenol data.

If the Kiselev isotherm is applied to type I isotherm data with the requirement that K_n be nonnegative, the data fitting exercise will always return an estimate for K_n that is not far from zero. If no constraint is placed on K_n , fitting the Kiselev isotherm to type I isotherm data will, in most cases, return a negative estimate for K_n . This mathematical property of the Kiselev isotherm is illustrated in Fig. 4, which depicts a series of type I curves simulated using a range of negative K_n values while holding the q_m and K_1 parameters constant. The Kiselev isotherm has the ability to generate a type I curve by letting K_n take on a negative value. This is the reason why many researchers have reported negative K_n values for their type I isotherm data. Hamdaoui and Naffrechoux [5] were puzzled by the negative K_n obtained from the linear fit of the 4-CP data, commenting that K_n by definition should not be negative. Because of its mathematical form, the Kiselev isotherm equation can assume a negative but meaningless K_n value in data fitting. We stress that a negative K_n value is physically nonsensical. As noted earlier, if there are no adsorbate-adsorbate interactions, K_n is equal to zero, and the Kiselev isotherm reduces to the Langmuir isotherm. If the adsorbate-adsorbate interactions are significant, the Kiselev isotherm will return a positive value for K_n . K_n will only become

positive if the Kiselev isotherm is applied to the right type of isotherm data. In the next section, we discuss what type of isotherm data will lead to a positive K_n value.

Fig. 4. Type I curves calculated from the Kiselev isotherm showing the effect of negative K_n values ($q_m = 100 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$; $K_1 = 0.1 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$).

4.2. Type V isotherms

In this section, we investigate the behavior of the Kiselev isotherm when K_n is a positive value. Fig. 5 shows simulated curves of the Kiselev isotherm calculated using different positive values of K_n and fixed values of the other two parameters ($q_m = 100 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$; $K_1 = 0.01 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$). It is evident that the simulated curves are of sigmoid or S-shaped form. They are convex downward close to the origin and exhibit an inflection point when approaching a horizontal asymptote, that is, a saturation region. This is the typical shape of a type V isotherm according to the IUPAC classification, encountered in gas-solid adsorption. It should be noted that certain combinations of the three positive parameters may make a type V isotherm resemble a type I isotherm. The Kiselev isotherm was devised by its eponymous creator to account for adsorption when adsorbate-adsorbate interactions are significant [2,3]. A type V isotherm is indicative of the presence of adsorbate-adsorbate interactions according to the Kiselev model. As such, the Kiselev isotherm should not be used to describe other isotherm shapes such as the type I

isotherms of 4-CP and phenol, which are always convex upward and cannot have an inflection point. As discussed above, the theoretical concept of adsorbate-adsorbate interactions breaks down when the Kiselev isotherm uses a negative K_n value to fit a type I isotherm. We mention in passing that several isotherm models developed for gas-solid adsorption are sometimes misapplied in liquid-solid adsorption, an example of which is the Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm [16].

Fig. 5. Type V (S-shaped) curves calculated from the Kiselev isotherm showing the effect of positive K_n values ($q_m = 100 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$; $K_1 = 0.01 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$).

Although type V isotherms are often encountered in gas-solid adsorption, there are only a few such observations in liquid-solid adsorption. Some examples of type V isotherms for aqueous adsorption systems have been discussed in a recent report [17]. To illustrate the ability of the Kiselev isotherm to describe aqueous type V isotherm data, it was fit to the equilibrium data of fluoride adsorption on a layered double hydroxide adsorbent [18]. Fig. 6 illustrates that the entire experimental S-shaped isotherm is well tracked by the Kiselev curve ($R^2 = 0.999$), which was calculated using unique and positive estimates for the three adjustable parameters ($q_m = 367.4 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$; $K_1 = 0.006 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$; $K_n = 20.06$). The Kiselev isotherm was applied to another set of aqueous S-shaped isotherm data, as depicted in Fig. 7. In this case, a multi-walled

carbon nanotube was used to remove methylene blue from aqueous solution [19]. As seen in Fig. 7, the Kiselev fit, calculated using positive estimates for the three parameters ($q_m = 597.6 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$; $K_1 = 0.014 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$; $K_n = 16.73$), agrees well with the experimental data, returning an R^2 score of 0.986.

Fig. 6. Kiselev fit compared to observed fluoride isotherm data reported by Lv et al. [18].

Fig. 7. Kiselev fit compared to observed methylene blue isotherm data reported by Ncibi and Sillanpää [19].

5. Conclusions

The problem of obtaining a negative association equilibrium constant K_n when the Kiselev isotherm is used to describe adsorption at the liquid-solid interface has been resolved. Because of its mathematical form, the Kiselev isotherm will return a negative value for K_n if it is applied to type I isotherm data. However, a negative K_n estimate has no physical meaning. The Kiselev isotherm was devised by its eponymous creator to account for adsorption when adsorbate-adsorbate interactions are significant. It predicts that adsorbate-adsorbate interactions will lead to a type V isotherm, which is convex downward at moderate concentrations and exhibits an inflection point when a certain surface coverage is reached and the isotherm turns toward saturation. Therefore, with a proper set of positive estimates for its three fitting parameters, the Kiselev isotherm can be used to track the shape of a type V isotherm. It should not be used to fit a type I isotherm, which is always convex upward and cannot have an inflection point. Because a type I isotherm by definition implies the absence of adsorbate-adsorbate interactions (one of the assumptions of the Langmuir model), fitting the Kiselev isotherm to such data should return a zero or near zero value for K_n . In this correct data fitting procedure, the Kiselev isotherm reduces to the Langmuir isotherm. In sum, many previous studies have misapplied the Kiselev isotherm by using it to fit type I isotherm data.

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Declaration of competing interest

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